

Deracination in the poem House and Land by Allen Munro Curnow

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Allen Curnow was a leading poet of New Zealand. His works are well known for the theme of displacement. It gives a firsthand experience of the issues that bothered the English settlers in New Zealand. House and Land is one of his famous works and is based on the same theme.

Allen Curnow ‘s House and Land investigates the sentiment of alienation experienced by the European immigrants. Even though they have used two generations in the selected land, they still felt displaced. Curnow indicates the theme of displacement, though the sellers dismissed from England to New Zealand. They failed to identify New Zealand as their inability to adapt to the place. Miss Wilson, the child of one of the immigrants, obtains herself charged with avoid. A Historian visits her home for research on the immigrants. He learns that the lady lives a luxurious life. She has grown old.

She cherishes the everlasting memories of her girlhood days spent in England. She is filled with pride at the photograph of a baronet uncle. It shows her pride in her ancestral heritage. A picture that portrays the big hall of her ancestral house also revealed her rich past. Her expansive building was equipped with all the necessary amenities of life. In spite of a stay for such a long time, she felt detached. Miss. Wilson represents the settlers who managed to adopt but failed to adapt.

The Cowman, a resident of the house, tells the historian about his long association with the family. He has been working for them from Miss. Wilson’s father ‘s days. Upon enquiring about the family background., he has no answer. His statement, he merely “lives,” shows his detachment. He has already made up his capacity to shift his working place next winter. He says that he is leaving the house because it is”bloody quiet”. The house lacks joy or merriment. It is haunted by utter hopelessness.

The historian then takes up the case of the tie-up dog within the compound. The dog was lying tied up “under the bluegums.” The phrase underscores the feeling of depression. The dog seems to be brooding and consuming itself. It just lazily rambles from privy to fowl house to a restroom. It senses the innate stagnation and a state of decay.

Miss. Wilson, her servants, and even the dog experience a sense of hollowness. The idea that the house might fall illustrates how fragile their spiritual situation was. The spirit of exile, concludes the historian, “Is strong in the people still. Miss. Wilson is obsessed with the past. The Historian senses that it is going to rain. Rain is some fertility and redemption. Though it rains, it does not bring contentment. The dog retires to its vessel, where it remains “lost and lame.” The word ‘lame’ suggests the advantage of the settlers as they missed their motherland. The settlers always felt themselves to be unfinished.

The poet voices his opinion through the Historian. The message is loud and clear. The settlers must move on and not cling to their past. Having adopted the country, they should adapt themselves accordingly. Things cannot change drastically, but the hope is there to be pursued.

In House and Land Allen Curnow emphasises the theme of displacement. Though the settlers removed from England to New Zealand, they failed to identify New Zealand as their homeland. Though they live in the selected land, they have not yet adapted to the circumstances. Unless they change their attitude, their life will remain miserable. The poet believes that the next generation will change. He presents it symbolically through the rain that occurs in the last stanza. Ole Miss. Wilson does not have anybody to carry on her legacy. With her end, the old connections too will end.

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